

IMPROVEMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL PROCESS ORGANIZATION AND MANAGEMENT TECHNOLOGIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: This article presents opinions and comments on the development of organizational structures of the personnel management system in educational institutions.

Key words: management, management, organizational work, structure, employees, organizational structure, order, discipline.

State educational standards define the basic state requirements for the necessary and sufficient level of education and the volume of educational loads. The state educational standard determines the knowledge, skills and qualifications that students should acquire. Also, the State educational standard serves as a control tool, a criterion that determines the conditions of the training courses of the educational institution.

As a result of the introduction of the educational standard, the state, as a customer, sets a task for educational institutions. Based on these tasks, the educational institution gradually determines what knowledge, skills and qualifications it should provide and how to implement them. Taking into account the above, the state educational standard, which represents the content of education in the training of teachers in the higher education system, has determined the following:

1. General requirements for professional pedagogical training and conditions for its implementation.
2. Student's educational obligations and their size.
3. Academic freedom of the educational institution in determining the content of professional training.
4. General requirements for the list of professional training courses (specialties).
5. The procedure for developing and approving minimum requirements for the level and content of professional training of graduates.
6. Rules for conducting state control over compliance with the requirements of the state educational standard.

N.A. Muslimov [4] It has been studied that motivational factor, intellectual factor, volitional factor, emotional factor, practical-objective factor, existential factor, self-management factor affect the professional formation of a teacher who is being trained in the direction of "Service".

The system of practical knowledge plays an important role in the development of the student's professional skills. One of the important aspects of this knowledge is that it divides reality into sections based on the criterion of subjectivity. While thinking faithfully works in every thinking process, it encourages local thinking and on this basis to choose the shortest way to achieve the goal, discarding unnecessary things and thoughts and working on the necessary thoughts.

This process, in turn, teaches to look for alternatives among the considered models, to compare one model with another model, and to give importance not only to the components themselves, but also to the design of the compared components. It is known that the

comparison is carried out on objects of the same gender, and a set of facts is created that makes general conclusions about the qualities and properties of the compared components and leads to the final result. This, in turn, helps to fill the bank of the system of thoughts and make it possible to use it.

In cooperation with the customers of educational institutions, development of curricula and higher education programs, including updated qualification requirements for educational areas and specialties, requirements for students' knowledge and qualifications, training of specialists; systematic study of requirements for the quality of training of specialists of production enterprises and organizations by professors and teachers of specialized departments of higher educational institutions directly participating in the formation of educational content, development and improvement of scientific and practical aspects of solving them; stages of implementation, intersectoral integration in ensuring the quality of personnel training and employment.

Education has a priority role in the production of human resources, because human capital is the main factor in the development of nations. The production function shows the relationship between the quantity of input and the intermediate factors for the production of a particular good, taking into account its quality. Economists focus on how educational institutions choose inputs and use resources to obtain a particular output. The question posed to education today is that production has lost its place as a unique function, especially in the educational system.

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